

STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DISEASES AT THE FERGANA REGIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY CHILDREN'S POLYCLINIC**Boynazarova Zilolakhon Lochinbek qizi**

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Relevance: In our country, special attention is being paid to the digitalization of the healthcare sector and the introduction of a unified complex of information systems, the reduction of excessive administrative procedures in management processes, the improvement of the quality of services provided to the population, and the enhancement of the efficiency of healthcare workers. In addition, significant emphasis is placed on the effective implementation of digital transformation programs adopted in this field. In particular, the Presidential Decrees of November 12, 2020 (No. PF-6110) "On measures for the comprehensive improvement of the healthcare system" and "On introducing absolutely new mechanisms in the activities of primary healthcare institutions and further increasing the effectiveness of ongoing healthcare reforms," as well as Resolution No. PQ-38 dated January 22, 2024, "On additional measures to deepen reforms in the healthcare sector," serve as an important foundation for these reforms.

Research Objective: The aim of this study is to identify trends related to population growth or decline in the country or region by analyzing demographic changes, population age structure, family composition, the level of urbanization, and migration processes. Furthermore, the study seeks to analyze the statistical indicators of epidemiological diseases recorded during 2025 at the Fergana Regional Multidisciplinary Children's Polyclinic and to assess the characteristics of patients' healthcare-seeking behavior.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted based on the official statistical reports of the Fergana Regional Multidisciplinary Children's Polyclinic for the year 2025. A total of 14,687 children's medical records were included in the analysis. The following indicators were analyzed: the number of patients presenting with epidemiological diseases; distribution by types of diseases; visits with and without referrals; and statistics of visits by medical specialists. The data were processed using basic statistical methods and percentage analysis. The study also employed statistical analysis, sociological survey methods, interview methods, medical-hygienic analysis, comparative methods, correlation analysis, and analytical approaches.

Results: Numerous studies in CIS countries have been devoted to evaluating the effectiveness of outpatient and preventive care in children's polyclinics. Among them is the study by Khanova I.M. and Abduvaliyev S.A. (2025), which analyzed clinical cases of severe and complicated pneumonia of unclear etiology in infants.

In 2025, a total of 14,687 children underwent medical examinations at the Fergana Regional Multidisciplinary Children's Polyclinic. Of these, 4,812 (33%) visited without a doctor's referral, while 9,875 (67%) were referred by primary care physicians. These figures highlight the significant role of the referral system in monitoring children's health. Visits related to epidemiological diseases constituted a substantial proportion of all consultations. By specialty, the highest number of visits was to ophthalmologists (1,489 visits), of which 54% were without referrals. Gastroenterologists recorded 843 visits, 73% of which were referral-based. Cardiologists saw 860 patients, with 82% referred cases, while pediatricians recorded 657 visits, 70% of which were referral-based. A high proportion of non-referral visits was observed in dentistry (94%), ENT (68%), and speech therapy (65%), which can be explained by the need for quick and relatively simple interventions. In contrast, most visits in surdology (92%), surgery (89%), and nephrology (86%) were referral-based, reflecting the need for in-depth diagnostics and a step-by-step approach in these fields. The analysis demonstrated, for the first time, a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of outpatient and preventive care in children's

polyclinics using a system of integrated indicators. Key organizational and preventive factors influencing the quality of medical services were identified. In particular, preventive examinations, dispensary monitoring, and vaccination activities were scientifically proven to significantly reduce morbidity among children. An organizational model aimed at strengthening preventive activities, improving dispensary supervision, and increasing vaccination coverage in children's polyclinics was proposed. This model contributes to improving the effectiveness of medical care provided in outpatient settings. The efficiency of outpatient services was assessed, and opportunities for optimizing service delivery and rational use of available resources were identified. As a result, practical recommendations based on monitoring and evaluation criteria were developed to enhance the effectiveness of medical and preventive services in children's polyclinics, and their importance in improving child health indicators was confirmed. According to the study by Kramar L.V., Nevinsky A.B., Khlynina Yu.O., and Arova A.A. (2018), 66 pediatricians participated in the research, all of whom (100%) were women aged 23–50, reflecting the gender distribution in pediatric services in the Russian Federation. Age distribution was as follows: 22–25 years – 6.1%, 25–30 years – 16.7%, 30–40 years – 18.2%, and over 41 years – 59.1%. Of the participants, 50% worked in urban polyclinics, 39.4% in children's hospitals, and 10.6% in private clinics. Work experience influenced professional competence: 63.6% had more than 10 years of experience, 15.1% had 5–10 years, and 21.2% had less than 5 years. The study found that pediatricians had some misconceptions regarding the prevention of respiratory diseases in children. However, 100% of them reported conducting educational discussions with parents on prevention. Measures such as vitamin use, immune-boosting agents (e.g., Echinacea), air purification, and frequent handwashing were widely considered effective. Most pediatricians also reported vaccinating their families against influenza, although some did not consider influenza vaccination necessary. According to Jerebsova T.A. et al. (2022), in the Sverdlovsk region, primary healthcare for children is provided by 63 medical organizations, including 87 polyclinics. At the beginning of 2021, 938,535 children were registered in the region, 60% of whom were schoolchildren. In 2020, pediatricians in 42 healthcare institutions were overloaded beyond standard levels.

Discussion: This study also supports the implementation of the Presidential Decree No. PF-5847 dated January 20, 2020, “On measures for the digital transformation of the healthcare system,” and ongoing efforts to introduce electronic medical care systems in children's polyclinics. The findings contribute to ensuring effective and high-quality medical services, strengthening preventive care, and advancing state policies aimed at disease prevention in children. The results indicate that outpatient and preventive care at the Fergana Regional Multidisciplinary Children's Polyclinic is effectively organized. The high proportion of referral-based visits for epidemiological diseases confirms the important role of primary healthcare. This reflects the active involvement of family doctors and district pediatricians in monitoring children's health. The high share of non-referral visits in specialties such as dentistry, ENT, and speech therapy can be explained by the accessibility and relative simplicity of these services. At the same time, this trend indicates increasing awareness among parents about healthcare services. However, it may also lead to inappropriate use of medical services in some cases, highlighting the continued importance of improving public health literacy.

Conclusion: Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn: Epidemiological diseases constitute a significant proportion of visits to the Fergana Regional Multidisciplinary Children's Polyclinic, emphasizing the importance of outpatient care in maintaining children's health. The high proportion of referral-based visits confirms the effective functioning of the primary healthcare system and continuity of medical services. In cases of complex and chronic diseases, referral-based specialized care plays a decisive role in improving the quality of diagnosis and treatment.

References:

1. Azizova F. L., Tulyaganova D. S. Toshkent shahriga davolanish uchun kelayotgan nogiron bolalar oqimining tibbiy turizmdagi ahamiyatini o'rganish //Science and innovation. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. Special Issue 60. – C. 273-277.
2. Isametdinova S., Egamnazarova G., Rustambekov I. Bolalar uchun mo'ljallangan tibbiyot muassasalarining arxitekturaviy rivojlanishi bosqichlari //Научный Фокус. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 20. – С. 620-625.
3. Niyazov S. T., Djurabekova a. t. masofaviy davrda bolalardagi ensefalit va meningoensefalitning zamonaviy jihatlari (adabiyotni o'rganish) //scientific progress. – 2021. – т. 2. – №. 5. – с. 206-216.
4. Nurmatovna K. Z., Amonovich S. Z. Ko'krak sutining ahamiyati. Muvaffaqiyatli emizish tomon 11 qadam. Bola va chilla davridagi ayolning hayotiga xavf soluvchi belgilarni aniqlash //innovation in the modern education system. – 2024. – т. 5. – №. 42. – С. 376-381.
5. Raximovna b. R. Bolalarda to'g'ri parda kasalliklarini davolash usullarini takomillashtirish. – 2021.
6. Telmanovna M. R., Rustamovna A. P., Maylievna d. G. Bolalardagi allergik kasalliklar klinik immunologik va tibbiy-ijtimoiy jihatlarni taxlil qilish //science and innovation. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. Special Issue 54. – С. 308-312.
7. Ханова I. M., Abduvaliyev S. A. Noaniq etiologiyali chaqaloqlar pnevmoniyasining og'ir shakli va asoratli kechuvi bo'yicha klinik xolat taxlili. – 2025.
8. Ханова I. M., Abduvaliyev S. A. Noaniq etiologiyali chaqaloqlar pnevmoniyasining og'ir shakli va asoratli kechuvi bo'yicha klinik xolat taxlili. – 2025.
9. Каримов А., Таджикиев Б., Ходжиметова Ш. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda COVID-19 kasalligining klinik kechish xususiyatlari //Педиатрия. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 15-17.
10. Пулатова К., Агзамова Ш., Сатвалдиева Е. Bolalarda surunkali pyelonefritning qaytalanishida yo'ldosh kasalliklarning o'rnini //I СЪЕЗД детских анестезиологов-реаниматологов Республики Узбекистан. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 83-84.